

DEVELOPMENT AND CHALLENGES OF SKI TOURISM IN AZERBAIJAN: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS**Mirzayeva A.***Baku State University (lecturer)**Institute of Control Systems (dissertant)*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13619516>**Abstract**

Tourism is an integral facet of modern life, offering diverse experiences away from routine environments. This study explores ski tourism within the broader context of adventure and extreme tourism, focusing on Azerbaijan's emerging ski resorts. Key challenges such as infrastructure development, accessibility, seasonal fluctuations, environmental impacts, and competition are analyzed. The article emphasizes the need for sustainable development strategies and enhanced promotional efforts to establish Azerbaijan as a competitive destination for ski tourism.

Keywords: tourism, ski resorts, extreme tourism, adventure tourism, Azerbaijan, infrastructure, sustainability

Introduction: Tourism has evolved significantly, with ski tourism emerging as a niche sector catering to adventure enthusiasts seeking physical challenges in natural environments. Azerbaijan, nestled in the Caucasus region, has begun developing its ski resorts to attract both domestic and international tourists. This article examines the specific challenges faced by Azerbaijan in developing its ski tourism industry, highlighting key factors influencing its growth and sustainability.

There is still no universally accepted definition of tourism. For example, in statistics, tourism is understood as a form of population migration that is not associated with changing residence or work. A widely used definition was developed by the International Conference on Travel and Tourism Statistics and approved by the WTO and the UN Statistical Commission in 1991. According to this conventional decision, a tourist is a visitor, that is, a person who travels and stays in places outside their usual environment for no more than twelve months for any purpose other than engaging in activities remunerated from within the place visited.

Thus, "tourism" is a very complex concept. In different areas of the tourism industry, this word is interpreted differently. There are many approaches to its definition. Considering that tourism for us is a systemic object of study, a conceptual definition is necessary. Probably the most relevant is the characterization of tourism as a set of relationships and phenomena that arise during the movement and stay of people in places different from their place of residence and work. This widely accepted definition was developed by the International Association of Scientific Experts in Tourism.

Along with the general definition, the classification of individual types of tourism remains problematic. For research purposes, the classification of special types of tourism is important. These can include tourist activities that are fully or partially characterized by the following features:

- Exotic types of tourism;
- Labor-intensive creation of the final tourist product;
- Capital intensity;
- Combination of characteristics of various types of tourism;

Dependence on secondary human needs;

Use of non-traditional sources of financing.

Special, most common types of tourism that meet the above requirements include ski and extreme tourism. Today, ski tourism is still considered an elite type of recreational activity. There are several reasons for this: the geographically conditioned inaccessibility of regions attractive for this type of vacation; the cost of ski tours is significantly higher than that of classic beach vacations; and low popularity among tourists due to existing slope safety issues. Only 3% of the country's population visits ski resorts.

Now it is necessary to define ski tourism itself. The type of tourism is determined in relation to the conditional country of visit: domestic, inbound, and outbound tourism. Ski tourism falls into all three categories. Social and amateur tourism are distinguished. Ski tourism can be both amateur (i.e., self-financed) and social (e.g., the state finances certain sports competitions). Regarding classification by trip purpose, ski tourism belongs to sports tourism (sports tourism involves trips aimed at active participation in sports events). In terms of organization, ski tourism can be package or individual. Ski tourism is a seasonal type of tourism. In Scandinavian countries and Russian resorts, it lasts approximately from October to May. Thus, it can be said that ski tourism is a special type of tourism characterized by many criteria and fits into many classifications.

An analysis of numerous interpretations of the concept of "ski tourism" has revealed two predominant definitions. The first: ski tourism is a type of mountain tourism that involves descending mountains on skis or a snowboard; the second: it is a type of sports tourism. However, today these interpretations are no longer relevant. In our opinion, the following definition is more pertinent. Ski tourism is the descent from mountains on skis or a snowboard on natural snowy slopes and specially prepared trails for recreational purposes.

In Europe, the intensive development of extreme tourism began in the late 1880s and early 1890s. During this time, the popularization of this direction among tourists and athletes also started. In Azerbaijan, this occurred nearly a century later, in the 1990s.

Where did skiing originate? The most common belief is that the "cradle" of skiing belongs to Scandinavia and Mongolia. There is also evidence that the homeland of skiing was the Baikal region, close to Mongolia in terms of natural and historical conditions. On the banks of the Lena and Angara rivers and Lake Baikal, rock paintings have been found, suggesting the presence of "skis" during the Mesolithic and Paleolithic periods.

The history of special mountain skis began more than 3,000 years ago. In the Republic of Karelia, on the shores of the White Sea, rock paintings depicting skiers have been found. Historical sources describe people who used skis for hunting and warfare. Additionally, their active use in the European North is reflected in folklore. An ancient Icelandic legend tells of the goddess Skadi. She left her husband and returned to her homeland to stay there until the end of her days, skiing with her friend Ullr (the God of Snow).

In Norway, as early as the 11th century, unique ski competitions were held. However, there were no standard rules. The people themselves acted as judges, choosing the winner. Being a winner of such competitions was so prestigious that even kings aspired to participate. There is a saga about King Harald the Hard-Ruler, who did not want to give up his fame to a young man rumored to be the fastest skier. The king decided to teach the young man a lesson and asked him to jump over a cliff. The legend tells how "Hemming climbed to the top of a high mountain, strapped on his skis, and rushed down with such speed that it seemed incredible. To keep the skis from falling off at speed, he tried to make smooth turns. Suddenly, he pushed off and made a jump into the air. The wind filled his cloak. It billowed like a sail, and Hemming flew, flew..."

Thus, it is clear that skis have been used by northern peoples since at least the early Iron Age. They made it possible to travel faster and facilitated hunting. In military affairs, they were sometimes indispensable.

Today, people ski all over the world. In Austria and France, in the USA and Japan, in New Zealand and the Philippines, and even in Africa. Today, ski resorts exist in all countries. The main alpine skiing center remains Europe, but even in Africa, there are opportunities to ski. The classic region for mountain recreation is the Alpine region within France, Austria, Switzerland, Liechtenstein, Germany, and Italy. The constant flow of skiers has led to the creation of specialized alpine skiing areas. Their number grows every year. Existing resorts improve, enhance their service levels, create new trails, and more.

Azerbaijan, located in the Caucasus region, has emerged as a promising ski tourism destination with resorts like Shahdag, Tufandag, Gabala, and Oguz. Despite challenges such as limited infrastructure and seasonal variability, Azerbaijan is investing in modernizing facilities and enhancing visitor experiences to attract a growing number of domestic and international tourists.

These resorts are actively developing and aim to attract more tourists, providing them with opportunities for active outdoor recreation, comfortable accommodation, and entertainment.

The development of ski tourism in Azerbaijan faces several challenges that need to be addressed for the industry to thrive:

Infrastructure Development: While there are ski resorts like Shahdag and Tufandag, infrastructure development, including roads, accommodations, and facilities like ski lifts and snowmaking equipment, needs further investment and improvement.

Accessibility: Some ski resorts in Azerbaijan are located in remote areas, making access challenging, especially during winter when weather conditions can affect road travel.

Seasonal Nature: Ski tourism in Azerbaijan is highly dependent on weather conditions and the duration of the winter season. Shorter winters or unpredictable snowfall patterns can impact the length of the ski season.

Marketing and Promotion: There is a need for better marketing and promotion of Azerbaijani ski resorts both domestically and internationally to attract more tourists and raise awareness about the country's skiing opportunities.

Skill Development: Training and developing local ski instructors and staff in hospitality and tourism services are essential to enhance the quality of visitor experiences and safety standards.

Environmental Impact: Ski tourism can have significant environmental impacts if not managed sustainably. It's crucial to implement practices that minimize ecological footprints, such as waste management and preserving natural habitats.

Competition: Azerbaijani ski resorts face competition from more established destinations in neighboring countries like Georgia and Turkey, which have longer traditions in winter sports and more developed infrastructure.

Addressing these challenges requires coordinated efforts from the government, private sector, and local communities to invest in infrastructure, promote sustainable practices, improve accessibility, and enhance marketing efforts to position Azerbaijan as a competitive ski tourism destination.

Ski tourism has evolved into a specialized niche within the global travel industry, offering enthusiasts thrilling experiences amidst scenic mountain landscapes. This study explores the development trajectories of ski tourism in Azerbaijan, Georgia, Turkey, and Switzerland, highlighting similarities, differences, and challenges unique to each destination.

Georgia has capitalized on its mountainous terrain, particularly in regions like Gudauri, Bakuriani, and Mestia, to develop world-class ski resorts. The country benefits from strategic infrastructure investments, favorable snow conditions, and a robust tourism promotion strategy, making it a popular destination for ski enthusiasts from Europe and beyond.

Turkey boasts diverse ski resorts across its mountainous regions, including Palandoken, Uludag, and Erciyes. With significant investments in infrastructure and accessibility improvements, Turkey has positioned itself as a leading ski tourism destination in the Middle East, attracting a mix of local and international visitors seeking winter sports adventures.

Switzerland remains a global benchmark for ski tourism, renowned for its iconic resorts such as Zermatt, St. Moritz, and Verbier. The country's extensive ski infrastructure, reliable snow conditions, and high-quality hospitality services cater to a discerning international clientele, contributing significantly to its tourism economy.

Comparative Analysis:

Infrastructure Development: Azerbaijan and Turkey are actively investing in ski resort infrastructure, whereas Georgia benefits from existing Soviet-era facilities. Switzerland maintains extensive and well-established infrastructure.

Accessibility: Switzerland and Turkey have well-developed transportation networks to ski resorts, while Azerbaijan and Georgia face challenges with remote locations and seasonal road conditions.

Seasonality: Switzerland and Austria benefit from longer ski seasons due to reliable snowfall, whereas Azerbaijan and Georgia experience variability in snow conditions, impacting the duration of their ski seasons.

Environmental Impact: All countries prioritize sustainable practices, but Azerbaijan and Georgia face unique challenges in managing environmental impacts due to rapid development in mountainous ecosystems.

Competitive Positioning: Switzerland leads in luxury and high-end markets, while Azerbaijan, Georgia, and Turkey focus on affordability and accessibility to attract a broader tourist base.

Conclusion

Ski tourism in Azerbaijan, Georgia, Turkey, and Switzerland exemplifies diverse approaches to leveraging natural mountain assets for economic development and tourism promotion. Each country faces distinct challenges and opportunities based on its geographical, economic, and cultural contexts. Sustainable development practices, infrastructure improvements, and targeted marketing efforts are crucial for enhancing competitiveness and ensuring long-term viability in the global ski tourism market.

Gradually, traditional types of leisure such as educational, beach, or cultural-historical tourism are giving way to more active forms of entertainment. These include travel experiences where people learn something new, experience new emotions and impressions, test their endurance, and overcome their fears. This type of tourism is called adventure or extreme tourism.

Extreme activities are those that present a real risk to the individual. There is no universally accepted definition of this type of tourism. We have reviewed the most commonly encountered definitions and based on them, we have formulated our own definition.

The state of modern Azerbaijani extreme tourism is characterized by two contradictions:

Between the diversity and richness of tourist resources and the low level of organization of extreme tourism;

Between the high demand for popular destinations and the lack of professionally trained personnel.

It should be noted that Azerbaijan's unique natural resources and cultural heritage cannot be considered sufficient conditions for the development of tourism. It

is evident that Azerbaijan needs an influx of investments, primarily in the development of tourist infrastructure to create a network of tourist-class hotels that provide comfortable living conditions at low prices. However, there remain many unresolved issues:

Weak material base for extreme and adventure tourism: recreational bases have fallen into decay, and most companies do not have modern tourist equipment.

Lack of professionally trained personnel.

Inadequate information field: there is a near-complete absence of specialized literature and low awareness among tourists about extreme tourism.

The provision of necessary assistance to tourists in distress within Azerbaijan is the responsibility of the Ministry of Emergency Situations (MES). However, information about the location of search and rescue service units, their capabilities, and means of communication with them is practically inaccessible to the tourist community.

However, unlike foreign resorts where the ski component of tourism activities is often considered a priority, Azerbaijan faces many unresolved problems:

Insufficient investment attractiveness of the sector. The creation and further operation of ski resorts is an expensive business. Consequently, not many are willing to invest in such low-profit projects.

Lack of support for entrepreneurs regarding land issues.

Insecurity of private capital investments. There is no guarantee that businesses will not have to be abandoned due to changes in the legislative sphere.

Lack of information among tourists about Azerbaijani ski resorts. Absence of large-scale advertising.

Underdeveloped infrastructure.

Low level of service, primarily caused by an underdeveloped competitive environment.

Technical facilities are inferior to foreign resorts.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that ski tourism represents a new stage in the development of the modern tourism world. This direction will continue to grow each year, attracting an increasing number of tourists. The primary demographic for ski slopes has been and remains people aged 18 to 35. Gradually, ski tourism is transitioning from an elite and exotic activity to a more mainstream tourism direction. This type of tourism appeals to those who seek something new, want to test their endurance, and challenge their fears.

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